

The Koan Asklepieion – An Alternative Story

Approaching Healing Rituals by Serious Gaming

Abstract:

This paper explores the spatial dynamics of the Koan Asklepieion by using healing rituals as a narrative framework for analysing the built environment of the sanctuary. While the sanctuary on Kos is traditionally analysed in terms of its axiality and scenographic architecture, such perspectives often overlook the role of individual actors and their embodied experiences. By shifting the focus to specific participants—their movements, perceptions, and ritual practices—space emerges as a relational and dynamic category shaped through interaction.

Drawing on epigraphic and literary evidence, the study (re)constructs a narrative centred on the priestess Kallistrate and her family as they engage in a healing ritual. This scenario highlights forms of movement and spatial use distinct from the highly choreographed processions of festival contexts, including the use of secondary paths and entrances. To visualise these alternative spatial experiences, the project employs a 3D model of the sanctuary developed in ArchiCAD and implemented in the Unreal Engine as a flexible research environment. This allows for ground-level, avatar-based exploration, incorporating movement, perspective, and atmospheric conditions.

By combining storytelling with immersive digital modelling, the paper demonstrates how serious gaming can function as a heuristic tool for rethinking ancient spatial practices. The results challenge conventional interpretations of Hellenistic architecture by emphasising non-axial movement, varied viewpoints, and the performative dimensions of ritual space. This approach offers broader methodological implications for the study of ancient built environments.

Paper:

The Asklepieion on the island of Kos,¹ dating to the 2nd century BC and distributed across three superimposed terraces on Mount Dikaïos (Fig. 1), is often used to illustrate the principles of Hellenistic architecture in the Eastern Mediterranean.² Its scenographic character and ability to form vistas when approached axially via the processional street and large monumental entrance have often been highlighted (Fig. 2).³ However, those perceiving such views and the circumstances in which they approached the architecture are not usually discussed. If they are mentioned at all, it is usually in a very general way ('the viewer'),⁴ and they are thus seen as acting within the material frame of the Asklepieion, but not actively contributing to the built space.

However, when the focus of the analysis shifts to the actors and their standpoints and viewpoints, space becomes a relational category.⁵ This encompasses landscape, architecture and living bodies, which shift in changing arrangements as actors move through and perceive the

¹ For a summary of its architectural development, compare Rocco 2017, 333–347.

² For example, see Lauter 1986; Pollitt 1987; Hellmann 2006; Winter 2006.

³ For example, see Winter 2006.

⁴ For example, see Gruben 2001.

⁵ Löw 2016.

built environment.⁶ In this regard, the question of whose perspective to take and whose steps to follow when analysing built space is of major importance, as different kinds of spatial arrangements are tied to different kinds of actions and the identity of the respective actors. This paper therefore asks which kinds of spaces are constituted at the Koan Asklepieion when specific actors (a priestly family), their movements, and their perceptions during a specific course of action (healing rituals) are taken into account.

Two groups of people have been referred to in connection with the Koan Asklepieion until now. The first group comprises the large number of people who took part in the famous Asklepieia festival every four years. We have a significant amount of epigraphic and literary data on this festival.⁷ The second group comprises individuals or small groups who visited the sanctuary in search of healing. It attracted many pilgrims from across the Mediterranean and beyond during most days of the year.⁸ While there is little evidence of the specific rituals connected to this, the famous fourth *mimambus* of Herodas provides a fairly good idea of the general course of events.⁹

In this regard, it is important to consider the difference between actions taken during a festival and those taken during an everyday healing ritual. The latter involves less choreographed movement by large groups of people, for example during a procession on the processional street. The former involves more individual movement by individuals and small groups, for example when entering the temple and placing a fee in the treasury. Furthermore, a group of inscriptions known as the *Iamata* of Epidauros indicate that people approaching the god during a healing ritual were not as restricted by a strict sequence of ritual steps. For example, there were certain periods between the offering of sacrifices and incubation (healing sleep), or between the offering of thanks and consumption of the sacrificial meal upon returning, during which people could wander about the sanctuary and view the votives and honorific statuary set up by previous visitors.¹⁰

Those interested in spatial peripatetics can explore the built space of the Koan Asklepieion by adopting a different perspective and venturing beyond the major routes and monumental accessways used during festivals. As shown on the map (Fig. 1), there were side trails and entrances from the hilltop of the Asklepieion (Fig. 3) that gave direct access to areas of interest for healing purposes, such as fountains for purification and sacrifices, a money box in Temple B for paying healing fees, and votives showing healed patients.

However, having the physical option of accessing a certain area via a side entrance or trail does not mean that you are allowed to do so, or even that you know it exists.¹¹ These side entrances and trails are usually remote and not clearly marked. This is where the strength of storytelling comes into play. The Asklepieion of Kos offers a wealth of epigraphical evidence about the identity of individuals or families. This information can then be used to construct the perspective of a particular individual (or, more accurately, an avatar; see below) within a scenario in which taking side entrances and trails is feasible (such as a priest). For the purposes of this paper, we will tell the story of the Asklepios priestess Kallistrate visiting the sanctuary with her daughter-in-law Nannakis and her grandson Parmeniskos¹² to ask Asklepios to protect the child's health. This scenario will then be used to critically reflect on the validity of the scenario for general space construction during healing rituals.

⁶ Reckwitz 2003, 282–301.

⁷ Paul 2013.

⁸ Paul 2013.

⁹ Herodas, *Mimiamb* 4 (compare Zanker 2009).

¹⁰ IG IV² 1, 121 no. 3–4; IG IV² 1, 122 no. 36.

¹¹ Müller 2024.

¹² IG XII 4, 2, 978.

However, to fully utilise such a story when studying the Asklepieion's spatial characteristics during various activities and events, we require an alternative method of visualising the space arrangements associated with off-centre and secondary entrances, as current reconstructions tend to focus solely on the main axes and show frontal and bird's-eye views. Therefore, a cross-disciplinary, DFG-funded research project called 'Dynamic Spaces: The Asklepieion of Kos during Feast and Healing Ritual' has been launched.¹³ This project began in January 2024 and will conclude in December 2026. It employs a storytelling approach alongside advanced visualisation techniques. Specifically, a 3D model of the Koan sanctuary has been created using ArchiCAD and imported into the Unreal game engine to build a flexible virtual research environment that can be analysed and adapted according to the research questions.¹⁴ The game engine enables the avatar (the priestess Kallistrate, in this case) to move more naturally from a ground-based perspective. In addition to locomotion, the engine also allows atmospheric conditions to be considered,¹⁵ as it can include changing daylight conditions (incubation preparations lasted until late evening, as written sources tell us).

The storyboard, resulting from the study of architecture and written sources (supervised by the project director, a classical archaeologist), and the application of game technology as a serious gaming heuristic tool (supervised by the cooperation partner, an architect specialising in digital humanities), tells a different story about the spatiality of the Koan Asklepieion. This method can be applied to other architectural complexes, provided they include sufficient architectural preservation and written evidence to consider specific individuals and their actions. These insights can then be used to inform current ideas about how Hellenistic architecture worked. As will be demonstrated, axuality and frontality, as inferred from ground plans, were only part of the story. Diagonal architectural arrangements and consciously articulated differences in altitude were also used to guide movement and perception, and for staging purposes.

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¹³ <https://www.geschkult.fu-berlin.de/en/e/klassarch/forschung/projekte/dynamische-raeume/index.html>.

¹⁴ Müller and Kim 2026.

¹⁵ The model is still under construction; therefore, the colour of the architecture and people has not yet been fully incorporated. The timeline anticipates a fully coloured model by August 2026.

- 1: lower staircase
- 2: propylon
- 3: lower stoa
- 4: niche fountain
- 5: middle staircase
- 6: fountain house
- 7: temple B
- 8: building D
- 9: altar
- 10: exedra
- 11: building E
- 12: upper staircase
- 13: temple A
- 14: sacred grove
- 15: upper stoa
- 16: steps

Fig. 1: Asklepieion of Kos, ground plan © Project Dynamic Spaces

Fig. 2: Asklepieion of Kos, vista from main entrance © Project Dynamic Spaces

Fig. 3: Asklepieion of Kos, side trail and side entrances © Project Dynamic Spaces